

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14066718

Impact Of Principal's Coordination And Communication Roles On Teachers' Job Performance In Public Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of principal's coordination and communication roles on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses guided the study. The design for the study was the descriptive survey. Mean and rank order statistics were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant using z-test statistics. The theoretical framework was based on the "human capital theory" propounded by Adam Smith and developed by Becker in 1964. A sample size of 146 principals, representing the entire population of all the principals from all the 268 public secondary schools in Rivers State was drawn using the stratified random sampling technique. The sample comprised 77 male principals and 69 female principals. A researcher - designed instrument titled: The Impact of Principals' Coordination and Communication Role on Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (TIPCCRTJPO) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by the researcher's supervisor and two experts in the Department of Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation at the University of Port Harcourt. The reliability index determined for the instrument using test-retest was 0.73. Summarily, the findings of the null hypotheses revealed that there is a significant difference between the ways principals' coordination and communication role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The study therefore concluded that principals' administrative role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that principals of public secondary schools should adopt appropriate leadership styles and skills to continuously ensure that their administrative performance remains effective.

Keywords: Coordination, communication, principal, teacher

INTRODUCTION

The achievement of principals relies on their administrative capacities and ability to make reasonable decisions for effective secondary school administration. Biasness of some teachers and poor academic performance of students in secondary schools could be attributed partly to poor administrative skills of school principals (Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018). This is because the principal is the head of the school and should be expected to perform certain expert and authoritative functions bearing in mind that the end goal will be determined by effective teaching and learning. Be it big or small, public or private, it is the leader who usually provides direction towards goals attainment. Unfortunately, principals' abilities and powers as the authoritative, specialized and pedagogical leader of the school have turned

into matter of worry as there are public outcry on how principal direct school activities. To accomplish school goals, a proficient and viable executive must head the school. In schools, be it public or private the administrator is most viewed as the principal (Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018).

In Nigeria, a principal heads secondary education; such head should have demonstrated quality and the information to accomplish his managerial goals. The principals are the custodian and bookkeeping officers of their various institutions. Mbipom (2006) states that they assume all routine jobs to accomplish all administrative tasks as leaders for achieving school objectives for posterity. Principals are the uncompromising leaders of their schools as well as administrators in whose hands lies the future of these institutions. In the school system, the duty of administration falls upon the principal. The principal co-ordinates and organizes the entire organ towards the achievement of goals. Being top on the hierarchy, his activities directly or indirectly affect every other factors in the system, the teachers, students and other non-teaching personnel. Principals' role performance to a great extent determines the effectiveness of the teachers in the performance of their job. In fact, his dealings transcend the boundary of school to government agencies like the school board, education commission as well as the host community. Each of these bodies has a role expectation of the principal and he must successfully pilot the boat of the school to fulfillment of goals.

Principals, who are charged with the responsibility of utilizing human and material resources in schools, need to have the ability to coordinate these resources in order to achieve the desired results. Nwankwo in Abduiraham (2014) explains coordination as a process whereby an orderly pattern of group effort is developed to ensure unity of action in the pursuit of common goals. Thus, a secondary school with various departments, units and individuals with different functions need to be properly coordinated to ensure that the set school objectives are achieved and to enhance teachers' job effectiveness of directing and achieving set educational goals without friction. Principals' decision-making role is an indispensable aspect of management and very essential for the success of instructional managers. It is therefore imperative that school principals be knowledgeable in decision making for effective school administration. This means that effective administration requires rational decision making which leads to the selection of the best way to reach anticipated goals. This ability to make rational decision has been limited by low inadequate knowledge of school administration (Hingari, 2006). Communication role is very necessary to a school administrator; reason being that it is process whereby administrative function which is organizing, planning and controlling can be achieved. According to Abraham (2013), communication is the process of passing information and understanding from one another. Communication in educational administration includes manager-employee, student-employee, teacher-teacher and teacher-student relationships

It has often been said that schools are as good as their principals. Sergon in Ambogo (2012) opines that schools success depends on the principals. According to him, a leader gets things done and has the ability to inspire, moderate, guide, direct and listen. These qualities are crucial for head teachers to be effective in their work.

The principal is required to know the basic principles of organization theoretically and practically. The organization theory includes understanding the organization, the division of labour, the organization goals, the delegation of authority, the work procedures, the formalization, teamwork, the job descriptions preparation, the organization structure and the span of control. In secondary school administration, principals are faced with multiple functions. They are constantly confronted with planned an unplanned event that occupy their available time, which can possibly result into success. For these reasons, principals need to possess certain administrative and supervisory roles to ensure teachers job effectiveness in Secondary Schools. Ajuzieogu (2008) studied bureaucratic impediments to principals' role performance in secondary schools in Abia State. Six research questions and six hypotheses were formulated for the study. The population of the study was 199 secondary schools. A sample size of 60 principals represented 30.15% was drawn from the population. The design for the study was a descriptive survey design. The instruments for the study are frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study revealed that bureaucratic principals' role performance negatively, division of labour frustrates efforts to initiate change. Recommendation was that the organizational structure of the schools in Abia State will be restructured in way that the principals will be given more opportunities to initiate their own ideas in performance of their roles in secondary

school. However, it is the gap in literature that necessitated a condition of scientific study on influence of principals' administrative role on teachers' job performance in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Stakeholders of public secondary education have continued to express worries over the persistent decline in the quality of administrative services of public secondary school in Rivers State. It is common to observe students loitering during school hours in the localities; teachers not doing what they ought to in the area of the record keeping and maintenance of discipline among students and so on. The high failure rate of students and indulgence in examination malpractice in Senior Secondary School Certification Examination and the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) are perhaps obvious indicators of inadequate administrative role of school principals. The above problems have led to a contention over the factors responsible for the lapses in the administration of public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. This contention over whether or not the principals are most guilty makes it expedient for one to ask if secondary school principals in Rivers State are administratively effective or ineffective in their roles. It is the quest to find out the factors militating against principal's coordinative and communication roles in terms of effectiveness or ineffectiveness that informed the researcher to consider some selected working conditions and how they affect principal's administrative roles in public secondary schools in Rivers State. However, principals' administrative roles such as coordination and communication, has a significant impact or relationship with the teachers' job performance. It is very clear that where there is a good educational planning, cogent school programme, what is most needed is good leadership role performance to coordinate all these for success. It is against this backdrop that the researcher examined the impact of principal's coordination and communication roles on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate impact on of principals' administrative roles on teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. Examine the ways principals' coordination role influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Identify the ways principals' communication role influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study

1. In what ways do principals' coordination role influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What are the ways principals' communication role influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The study was anchored on the following hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' coordination role influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' communication role influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Concept of Teachers' Job Performance

In the contemporary society, teachers occupy vital positions of honour and are regarded to be a major determinant of the societal values, intellectuals and moral development. It is often said that the standard and quality of education of a given nation is dependent and determined by the standard of her teachers. It is on this note therefore, that the federal government in 2004 deemed it necessary to review National Policy on education to include teachers' education (training) (Federal Republic of Nigeria FRN, 2013). This implies that teachers at every level of education must strive towards effectiveness since they are the building blocks of any society.

Teacher's job effectiveness refers to the degree of which teachers' carryout their primary duties of teaching profession and their activities (Owan, 2012). For a teacher to be called effective, the teacher must be punctual to school, have good knowledge of his subject matter, good communication skills, good interpersonal relationship with both staff and students, dresses modestly, effectiveness itself refers to the degree to which objectives are achieved and the extent as which targeted problems are solved. In contrast to efficiency, effectiveness is determined without reference to costs and, whereas efficiency means "doing the thing right", effectiveness means "doing the right thing"

After assessing all these qualities, it has been observed that many teachers in most secondary schools in Rivers State do not appear to have met such criteria effectively. Many teachers show unprofessional attitudes to work in the areas of absenteeism, time management, disciplining the students, communication skills, most of them do not know how to adequately carryout their instructions because of poor knowledge of their subject matter and are also ignorant of the best teaching method to use at that level. They go as far as disobeying the administrators when assigned to perform a duty, poor note writing and more unethical behaviours. Those poor attitudes of most teachers in the area have contributed to the fall in the standard of education and the poor academic performance of students in both internal and external examinations. Many teachers have in the past attributed their ineffectiveness to be as a result of the principal and vice principal's strict administrative role, leadership style, low salary structure, inadequate provision of facilities, poor teaching aids, unconducive environment, poor retraining programme for skill acquisitions and improvement and so on. However, with recent improvement by the government in terms of timely payment of salaries, coupled with other efforts being made in terms of supervision, one expects to see a positive change in the job effectiveness level of teachers.

Accordingly, Darling Hammond (2010) define an effective teacher as one who is intellectually challenging, motivating students, setting high standards and encourages self- Initiating learning. Anderson (2004) views an effective teacher as those teachers who achieved the goals set for them er goals set for them by others like the Ministry of Education. Effective teachers are very important for students learning. However, teachers' effectiveness is difficult to define since there has not been a consensus agreement on what measured quality teacher (Strong. Ward & Grant, 2011). However, it is possible to measure some teachers' attribute like interaction with students, teaching strategy, motivation with student, teaching strategy, motivation, pedagogical content knowledge and classroom management through qualitative research approach. These teachers" attributes could act in a long way to determine teachers' effectiveness. Strong. Ward and Grant (2011) identify four dimensions that were used to characterize an effective teacher as follows:

1. Instructional effectiveness
2. Uses of assessment for student learning
3. Positive learning environment and
4. Personal quality of the teacher

All these point to the fact that where teachers are adequately coordinated and monitored in the above listed ways, their performances improve to the benefit of the students. However, it has been observed that principals often times do not devote adequate time to important aspect of their school management assignments. Therefore, lack of supervision would contribute an obstacle in teachers" job effectiveness.

Principal Communication Role on Teachers' Job Performance

Communication in the wire that all and sundry is every organization. This wire may not be physical as the cave may be, but its usefulness surpasses all other concepts in the organization. The effectiveness of communications in every organization determines the extent the organization can thrive. Communication lubricates activities and also propels activities within an organization Communication can be referred to as the exchange of information considered as be helpful to the organization sent across to those who make up the organization with desired feedback from the receiver who are members of the same organization. In the words of Abraham (2013) communication is the act of inducing others to interpret an idea in the manner intended by the speaker of interpreter. Suffice to say that communication in this context portrayed to be an enclosed or encoded content requiring decoding. Abraham (2013) in a simplified way for comprehensive purpose, defined communication as any initiated behaviour on the part of the sender which conveys the desired meaning to the receiver

and causes desired response behaviour from the receiver, and also the process of passing information and understanding from one person to another. Communication mole is a skill available to the principal in the discharge of his administrative duties for teachers' job effectiveness. Principals seem to have issues with this skill because of the demands attached to it. The rigorous nature of communication could be misunderstood especially when information is not properly disseminated. Communication skill which a principal need covers a number of steps. Such steps are called channels. Abraham (2013) defined channels as the mode of transmission. It is required but for communication to be appropriate, it must be efficient and effective. However, channels of communication could be the

1. **Downward Communication Channels:** Sunward flow of communication follows the line of authority from top to the bottom of the organization's hierarchy. Tradition importance of this channel is to convey super-ordinate orders and directives to the subordinate below with expectation that these orders will be sufficient to stimulate and motivate teachers in the school system to accomplish the desire results.
2. **Upward Communication Channels:** upward communication channels represent the flow of information from the lowest in the organization hierarchy to the highest. This channel requires a superior to reinforce his statement, encouraging disclosure with consistent action. In such channels, subordinates express themselves freely, the superior must act in such a way that they will find the situation rewarding or at least non- threatening
3. **Lateral Horizontal Communication Channels:** This involves communication that takes place at same levels of hierarchy in an organization. It applies to communication between peers or managers at some levels.
4. **Diagonal Communication Channels:** This is communication that takes place between a manager and employees of another workgroup
5. **External Communication Channels:** Communication that takes place between a manager and external group such as banks, suppliers, vendors, etc.

To understand that communication does a variety of functions in such a way that the principal cannot do away with, Peretomode (2012) contributed while explaining the purpose of communication he saying that of all the management activities, none takes so much time as that of communication. Communication to him can alter the whole process of an organization thereby making it alterly purposeless. The need for communication as it is relevant to the principal are outlined as expressed by Peretomode (2014) thus:

To persuade, to instruct, to direct, to request, to present, to serve as information input or exchange, to stimulate or motivate staff, to develop an understanding, to produce and regulate activities aimed at doing primary task of the organization eg. in school, for the purpose of effective teaching and learning, to innovate, to assess outcomes, to socialize participants, to influence the performance of organizational members, to clarify and express feelings and, to control (p. 13)

Where the above points are not in the judicious use of the principal, there is bound to be chaos and conflict of duties, and in turn jeopardizes teachers' job performance.

There are barriers that arise in Principals' Communication, which include:

1. **Intrapersonal Factors:** This factor is made up of two components.
 - i. Selective perception: According to Donnelly, Gibson and Mancervich in Peretomode (2012) occurs when people block out or distort new information especially if it conflicts with what they believe.
 - ii. Difference in communication skills, occur in the differences in ability to develop and apply basic communication skill.
2. **Interpersonal Factors:** This category includes climate, trust, credibility and send receiver similarity.
 - i. Climate: This is the relationship between the superior and subordinate arising from the attitude and treatment each receives from the other.
 - ii. Distrust: This is as a result of lack of credibility, distrust and suspicion between a superior and subordinate can lead to less likelihood effective communication

- iii. Sender- receiver similarity: The similarity between the sender and the receiver in terms of age, sex, intelligence, socio-economic status and common attitude will affect communication
- iv. Different perception: Perception differs and this is caused by different frames of reference. This may be in form of encoding and decoding an information.
- 3. **Organizational Factors:** Such factors are referred to as barriers to communication which are hierarchical differentiation, school size, time, pressure, network breakdowns and status difference.
 - i. Hierarchical differentiation: The taller the organization the more difficult it becomes for information to get to those at the lower cadre of the organization, Information becomes slow as it takes time to get people at the very low end because of the expanded nature of the organization.
 - ii. Condensation: This is the tendency that information becomes shorten and précised as to get to everyone within the organization and the ability to act upon it faster.
 - iii. Closure: This refers to the tendency to relayers of ambiguous messages, such as rumours, to fill in, that is close gaps in the information that they are transmitting
- 4. **Size of the workforce:** The force of the school (administrators, teachers, and other non-academic staff) is likely going to affect the accuracy of communications
 - i. Time pressure: The many deadlines that must be met by the administrators, teachers and ochers in schools create time pressures and to a large extent constrains and individuals' ability for communication
 - ii. Network breakdowns: Another factor that can affect communication role of the principal in school is network breakdown. For example, a misplace memo or letter or message not received at appropriate time by the right person can cause relay of the piece of information.
 - iii. Status problem: This is as a result of block upward communication because sometimes, subordinates do not wish to express an option that is different from that of the principal.
- 5. **Technological Factors:** Because of the overloaded nature of certain information, it is sometimes difficult for principals to make a decision.

Principal's Coordination Role on Teachers' Job Performance

We should recall that administration deals with coordinating the activities of a group of people in an organization who make use of material resources to achieve organizational goals. Coordinating therefore means harmonizing or blending together all the activities of staff members in line with organization goals. Through coordinating individual objectives and differences can be harmonized with group objectives to ensure a cooperative venture in carrying out organizational tasks. In coordinating, various parts of the work should be linked together for harmonious relationship. The efforts of workers should be unified so that activities of all the sides of the system would aim at achieving common objectives (Nnabuo, Okorie &Ogar 2004). Administrators or principals are charged with the responsibility of effective use of men, materials and money (human and materials resources) to achieve the purpose of the organization It is therefore the duty of the administrators as instructional leaders to integrate each part of the organization towards Joint effort in order to succeed and to enhance teachers job performance. The administrators should therefore possess the ability to interpret the functions of planning, organizing, staffing and directing into a unified whole. In the school system, some staff may interpret similar interest and policies differently, which could hamper the realization of organizational goals. It is therefore the day of the administrator to always reconcile such differences and interests so that individuals and organizational goals can be achieved. School heads should make sure that teachers work towards common purpose rather than antagonize one another.

Denyer in Nnabuo (2004) is of the view that coordination could be achieved through the following means.

- 1. Appointment of powerful overall leaders that would ensure that common policies are followed.
- 2. Regular progress meeting of the heads of department, subject specialists, and educational administrators.
- 3. Providing clearly defined policies and communicating them to all concerned.
- 4. Having functional officers that could coordinate the supply and maintenance of plants, human and material resources.

5. Organizing inter-departmental training, seminars and workshops
6. Having a sound organization
7. Setting up committee for achieving coordination
8. Encouraging good morale in the system (p.10)

In all, the fact is that where teachers are adequately coordinated and monitored in the above listed ways, their effectiveness improves to the benefit of the students. Teachers' effectiveness are key components in any school system and successful teaching is one of the propellers for school change. Teachers' adequacy is referred to as far as emphasis on students' results, teaching and learning in the classroom are concern which advance better students' academic performance. A teacher is successful in the event that he/she can perform the set objectives and selected activities as per school goals. To sum up, in the school system the instructional leaders (the school heads) including the supervisor and inspectors monitor the activities of staff members so that teaching and learning can be improved. If workers are not doing well the instructional leaders can recommend minia conferences, workshops to improve and best productivity. Effective coordination therefore requires that the administrator should not rest in his cars, but he up and doing to oversee the workers activities as well as communicate effectively to them.

Human Relations Theory

Human Relations Theory stated that in addition to finding the best technological strategies to improve output, it was beneficial for administration to consider the human elements in the organization. The human relations theory was propounded by Mary Packer Follet in 1933. The theory was concerned with the human problems encountered in organizations such as welfare, motivation, retirement benefits among others and therefore concluded that such problems can only be minimized when there is co-operation among workers. Based on this, she developed four organizational principles, all of which centre on co-ordination: coordination by direct contact with the people concerned, coordination in the early stages, coordination as the reciprocal relation of all the factors in a situation, and coordination as a continuing process. The human relations theory has its central idea that the human factor is very important in the achievement of organizational goals. The proponent of this theory holds the view that workers will achieve better if their personal welfare was taken into consideration. Human relations theory is related to the present study because it buttresses the fact that the administrative arm of any organization especially the school should consider the welfare of the employees as utmost importance. Therefore, for effective secondary school administration in Rivers State to be actualized, the interest of teachers and other employees should be a priority.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was the descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised all the 268 public secondary schools across the 23 local government areas in Rivers State. A sample size of 146 principals, representing the entire population of all the principals from all the 268 public secondary schools in Rivers State was drawn using the stratified random sampling technique. The sample comprised 77 male principals and 69 female principals. A researcher - designed instrument titled: *The Impact of Principals' Coordination and Communication Role on Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (TIPCCRTJPQ)* was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by the researcher's supervisor and two experts in the Department of Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation at the University of Port Harcourt. The reliability index determined for the instrument using test-retest was 0.73. Mean and rank order statistics were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant using z-test statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question one: *In what ways do principal's coordination role impact on teachers' job performance in Public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Weighted mean, standard deviation and rank order statistics on the ways principal's coordination role impact on teachers' job performance in Public secondary schools in Rivers State.

S/No	Items	Male=77 Principals \bar{x}_1	SD ₁	Female=69 Principals \bar{x}_2	SD ₂	Mean Set \bar{x}_2	Rank	Remarks
1.	Organizing the entire organ towards the achievement of goals.	4.18	1.78	3.14	1.60	3.66	1 st	Agreed
2.	Harmonizing together the activities the activities of staff members in line with organization	4.02	1.74	2.77	1.67	3.40	2 nd	Agreed
3.	Ensuring that teachers work towards a common purpose.	3.36	1.73	2.76	1.67	3.06	3 rd	Agreed
4.	Reducing the rate of conflict in schools to enhance effectiveness.	2.67	1.63	3.09	1.76	2.87	4 th	Agreed
5.	Organizing inters department training.	2.89	1.70	2.59	1.61	2.74	5 th	Agreed
	Grand mean (x)	17.10	8.58	14.35	8.31	15.75		
		3.42	1.72	2.87	1.66	3.15		

Table 1 revealed that items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 with mean scores of 3.66, 3.40, 3.06, 2.87 and 2.74 respectively were above the criterion mean 2.50, thus, were accepted as the ways principal's coordination role influence teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Rivers State. On ranking, items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 ranked first, second, third, fourth and fifth respectively. The result of the analysis implied that that organizing the entire organ towards the achievement of goals, harmonizing together the activities of staff members in line with organization goals, ensuring the teachers work towards a common purpose, reducing the rate of conflict in schools to enhance effectiveness and organizing inter-department training are the ways principal's coordination role influence teachers job performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question two: *What are the ways principals' communication role impact teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Weighted mean, standard deviation and rank order statistics of male and female principals on the impact of principals' communication role on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

S/No	Items	Male=77 Principals \bar{x}_1	SD ₁	Female=69 Principals \bar{x}_2	SD ₂	Mean Set \bar{x}_2	Rank	Remarks
6.	Building synergy in the school system	3.06	1.75	4.34	1.76	3.79	1 st	Agreed
7.	Creating an enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals	2.87	1.69	2.73	1.65	2.80	4 th	Agreed
8.	Creating mutual understanding in the school system.	2.84	1.69	4.31	1.74	3.59	2 nd	Agreed
9.	Breaking information down to the level of everyone to achieve target goals.	3.22	1.70	2.42	1.52	2.82	3 rd	Agreed
10.	Carrying everyone along in the school system.	1.81	1.35	2.89	1.70	2.35	5 th	Disagreed
	Grand mean (x)	13.82	8.18	16.70	8.37	15.26		
		2.76	1.67	3.34	1.67	3.05		

On table 2 above, 16, 17, 18, and 19 had mean scores 3.70, 2.80, 3.59 and 2.82 respectively above the criterion mean of 2.50. This indicated that item 16, 17, 18 and 19 were accepted by the respondents as the ways principals' communication role impact teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Item 16 ranked first, item 18, 19 and 17 follow respectively as second, third, and fourth item 5 was last in the table coming fifth in ranking. This showed that the ways principals communication role impact teachers job performance in secondary schools in Rivers State are through building synergy in the school system, creating an enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals, breaking down information to the level of everyone to achieve target goals. On the other hand, carrying everyone along in the school system is not a way principal's communication role impact on teacher's performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' coordination role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: z-test analysis of the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' coordination role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Category	N	X	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Remarks
Male	77	3.42	1.72				
Female	69	2.87	1.66	144	1.96	+1.96	Significant

Table 3 showed that male principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.42 and 1.72 respectively while female principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.87 and 1.66 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 144 at an alpha significant level of 0.05, the calculated z-value of 1.96 equals the critical z-value of 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. By implications, there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' coordination role impact teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' communication role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test analysis of the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' communication role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Category	N	X	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Remarks
Male	77	3.14	1.71				
Female	69	2.89	1.69	144	2.07	+1.96	Significant

Table 4 showed that male principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.14 and 1.71 respectively while female principals have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.89 and 1.69 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 144 at an alpha significant level of 0.05, the calculated z-value of 2.07 is greater than the critical z-value of 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. By implications there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' communication role impact teachers' job performance in public secondary school in Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

The following are the summaries of the findings based on data presented and analyzed in the chapter.

1. It was found that organizing the entire organ towards the achievement of goals, harmonizing together the activities of staff members in line with organization goals, ensuring that teachers work towards a common purpose, reducing the rate of conflict in schools to enhance effectiveness and organizing inter-department training are the ways principals' coordination role impact on teacher's job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' coordination role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

3. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways principals' communication role impact on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Ways Principals' Coordination Impact on Teachers Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools

It was found that organizing the entire organ towards the achievement of goals, harmonizing together the activities of staff members in line with a common purpose, reducing the rate of conflict in schools to enhance effectiveness and organizing inter-department training are the ways principals' coordination role influences teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. This finding is in line with that of Nnabuo, Okorie and Ogar (2004) who asserted that through coordinating individual objectives and differences can be harmonized with group objectives to ensure a cooperative venture in carrying out organizational tasks. In coordinating, various parts of the work should be linked together for harmonious relationship. These efforts of workers should be unified so that activities of the sides of the system would aim at achieving common objectives. They further maintained that for effective coordination, the administrator should know the school's goals, task areas of staff members, materials and physical facilities for task performance and availability of funds to achieve set goals.

Ways Principals' Communication Role Impact on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools

Ways principals' communication role influences teachers' job performance in the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State are through the ability of the principals to build synergy in the school, creating an enabling atmosphere for both teachers and principals, creating mutual understanding in the school system and breaking information down to the level of everyone in order to achieve target goals. The above finding revealed that principals' communication roles are needed by principals for organizational harmony (Ajayi, 2007). In the same vein, Orji (2017) who carried out an empirical study on the impact of capacity building skills for administrative effectiveness of principals in secondary schools in Abia State found that principals regularly utilize communication skills in soliciting beliefs and ideas, advocating position and persuading others in order to achieve the desired administrative performance within the school. This finding according to Kokach (2006) implies that principals' communication role is the ingredient, which makes the activities of a school possible and also serves as the vehicle through which the basic management and administrative functions of a principal are carried out smoothly. The tested hypothesis revealed that male and female principals agreed that principals' communication role influences teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that principals' administrative role impact teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, coordination and communication roles significantly contribute to teachers' job performance in the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Also, there is need for effective coordination of activities to ensure that teachers work towards a common purpose.
2. In the same vein, principals' forms of communication role should be concise and easy to understand in order to aid the schools achieve its goals of teaching and learning.

REFERENCES

- Abraham, N.M. (2013). Educational administration in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Education Administration and Policy Studies*, 5(9), 50-81.
- Aderonmu, F. & Ehiamentolor, B. (2005). Roles of head teacher in academic achievement in secondary schools in Vihiga District, Kenya. *Journal of Social Science*, 3: 84 — 92.
- Ajuzieogu, C.B. (2008). *Bureaucratic impediments to principals' role performance in secondary school in Abia state*. An unpublished M.Ed dissertation, Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State.
- Ambogo, M.M. (2012). The impact of head teachers' administrative factors on performance in secondary school science subjects in Eldoret Municipality, Kenya. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)* 3(4) 514-52. [http://citeseerxist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.301.9063 & rep = rep Hype = pdf](http://citeseerxist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.301.9063&rep=rep1&context=1) accessed on October 15,20 17.
- Anyanniyi, D. (2016). The effects of transformational leadership on organizational conditions and student engagement with school. *Journal of Education Administration*. 38 (2), 112-129.
- Becker, G.S. (1964). *Human capital. A theoretical and empirical analysis with special reference to education*. The University of Chicago Press.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2010). *Evaluating teacher effectiveness. How Teacher Performance Assessment can Measure and Improve Teaching*. Centre for American Progress.
- Enaohwo, B. & Eferkeya, M. (2009). *Effectiveness of supervision and inspection in selected secondary schools in Kiambu Districts*. Unpublished M.Ed. Theses, Kenyatta University, Nairobi.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National policy on education*. Lagos; NERDC. <http://www.worldbank.org/dosted/policy/nastional/leg-ohtml>. Retrieved on 28th January 2011.
- Gant, D., Strong, O. & Ward, S. (2011). *Portability of teacher effectiveness across school settings*. National Centre for Analysis of Longitudinal Data in Education Research, Working Paper 77.
- Hinjari, H.S. (2006). Contemporary issues and challenges in the management of education. *Nigeria Journal of Education Management and Planning*, 2 (1), 123 - 126.
- Kokach, R. (2006). *The validity and reliability of the teachers' performance evaluation scale*. *Educational Sciences: Theory practice*, 6(3): 799-808.
- Mbipom, G. (2006). *Educational and administrative planning*. University of Calabar Press.
- Nnabuo, P.O.M, Okorie, N.C., Nwedeeduh, S.B., & Uche, C.M. (eds). (2006). *Leadership and supervision in education*. Giebon & Sons Press Port Harcourt.
- Onyeike, V.C. & Nwosu, C.M. (2018). Principals' administrative and supervisory roles for teacher's job effectiveness secondary schools in Rivers State. *British Journal of Education* 6(38-49).
- Orji, U. W. (2017). *Capacity building skills for administrative effectiveness of principals in secondary schools in Abia State*. An Unpublished Masters Dissertation submitted to the Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State.
- Owan, V.J. (2012). *Some causes of poor performance of pupils in primary school mathematics. A case study in Akamkpa L.G.A Cross River State*. Retrieved from <https://goggle/NTTxqc>
- Peretomode, V. F. (2014). *Theories of Management: Implication for educational administration*. University Printing Press.
- Peretomode, V.F. (2012). *Educational administration: Applied concepts and theoretical perspectives*. Toja Educational Research and Publishers, Ltd.
- Peter, A. (2014). *Managerial skills development and organizational performance: A study of selected manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt*. An unpublished Master's dissertation submitted to the department of management sciences, Faculty of management sciences, University of Port Harcourt.